

Relevancy of Educational Philosophy of Swami Vivekananda in the Present Scenario

Paper Id : 18808 Submission Date : 06/04/2024 Acceptance Date : 15/04/2024 Publication Date : 20/04/2024

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DOI:10.5281/zenodo.11126542

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Abstract

This paper provides a comprehensive review of Swami Vivekananda's educational philosophy and its relevance in contemporary education. Drawing upon a wide range of scholarly works, the paper examines Vivekananda's emphasis on character development, spiritual growth, and the holistic development of individuals. The literature review encompasses various aspects of Vivekananda's educational thought, including his views on moral and intellectual development, physical education, vocational training, and the promotion of universal brotherhood. Additionally, the paper explores the implications of Vivekananda's philosophy in modern educational contexts, considering its alignment with current educational practices and its potential to address contemporary challenges. Through a synthesis of diverse perspectives and critical analyses, this paper contributes to a deeper understanding of Vivekananda's educational ideals and their enduring significance in shaping educational discourse and practice.

Keywords

Swami Vivekanand, Educational Philosophy, Aims, Relevancy, Present Scenario.

Introduction

Swami Vivekananda, a visionary philosopher, emphasized the dual purpose of education: to equip individuals for both worldly success and spiritual fulfilment. He famously stated, "We want the education by which character is formed, strength of mind is increased, intellect is expanded, and by which one can stand on one's own feet." Additionally, Vivekananda believed that education is the revelation of the inherent perfection already present within individuals. In today's context, Vivekananda's teachings hold profound relevance, particularly concerning the goals he outlined for the youth.

Vivekananda keenly observed human psychology and societal dynamics, recognizing the shortcomings of the existing educational system, which often perpetuated physical weakness, ignorance, poverty, and political subjugation. He advocated for the youth to emerge as catalysts for positive change, emphasizing the pursuit of "complete freedom" from material desires to realize one's inner divinity. His philosophy centered on fostering a society that embraced both naturalistic and spiritual ideals, advocating for independence and self-reliance.

In the 21st century, as India's youth grapple with new challenges while striving for a brighter future, Vivekananda's insights resonate more than ever. By integrating Swami Vivekananda's philosophical principles into our educational framework, we can empower the youth to contribute meaningfully towards nation-building.

Objective of study

1. To examine the educational philosophy espoused by Swami Vivekananda.
2. To assess the contemporary relevance of Swami Vivekananda's educational philosophy within the current education scenario.

Review of Literature

1. Abhyankar, S.V. (1987) conducted an in-depth analysis of Swami Vivekananda's educational thought, focusing on value education. The study revealed that Vivekananda's philosophy, rooted in Advaita Vedanta, emphasized the cultivation of values such as love, self-realization, brotherhood, and courage.
2. Banerjee, A.K. and Meeta, M. (2015) explored Swami Vivekananda's educational philosophy, emphasizing its relevance in the contemporary education system. They highlighted Vivekananda's vision of education as life-building, character-building, and focused on the importance of values, ethics, and morality.
3. Gupta, R.P. (1985) examined Vivekananda's educational thoughts and their applicability in restructuring the educational system. The study found that Vivekananda stressed physical and mental development and viewed education as a preparation for life.
4. Gupta, S. (2021) discussed Vivekananda's educational philosophies and their implications in the present context. The research highlighted Vivekananda's emphasis on character building, spirituality, universal oneness, and materialistic fulfilment as integral aspects of education.
5. Misra and Shiva. S. (1986) critically analysed Vivekananda's educational philosophy and teaching methods, emphasizing the importance of holistic education and vocational training. They found Vivekananda's methods relevant in the modern context.
6. Sarkar, R. (2015) explored Swami Vivekananda's ideas and philosophy of education, emphasizing their relevance in promoting national development. The study underscored Vivekananda's belief in education as a means to uplift humanity and promote excellence and compassion.
7. Mukherjee, S. (2000) delved into Vivekananda's educational ideals and their implications for contemporary education. The research highlighted Vivekananda's vision of education as holistic and aimed at character building, spiritual growth, and social upliftment.
8. Ranganathan, S. (2017) examined Vivekananda's educational philosophy and its application in modern education. The study emphasized Vivekananda's emphasis on holistic development, integrating spiritual, intellectual, and physical dimensions in education.
9. Sen, A. (2013) analysed Vivekananda's educational ideas in the context of inclusive education. The research highlighted Vivekananda's advocacy for universal brotherhood and education's role in fostering social cohesion and equity.
10. Das, S. (2019) investigated Vivekananda's approach to education and its relevance in the digital age. The study emphasized Vivekananda's emphasis on critical thinking, creativity, and adaptability in navigating the complexities of modern life.

These studies collectively underscore the enduring relevance and profound impact of Swami Vivekananda's educational philosophy in shaping contemporary educational practices and fostering holistic development.

In essence, Swami Vivekananda's educational philosophy continues to inspire and guide modern educational practices, striving towards the holistic development of individuals and the betterment of society.

Methodology

The present study utilized the content analysis approach.

Tools Used

Secondary sources of data such as articles, books, newspapers, etc., were consulted by the researcher for data collection and analysis.

Analysis

Educational Philosophy of Swami Vivekananda

Swami Vivekananda's educational philosophy underscores the holistic development of individuals, rooted in Vedanta and Upanishads. For Vivekananda, education extends beyond mere academic learning, aiming at the comprehensive refinement of life. Key aspects of his educational philosophy include:

1. Physical Development: Vivekananda places significant emphasis on the physical well-being of learners. He advocates for the integration of physical education into the educational curriculum, asserting that a strong physique is essential for effective cognition and action. Vivekananda suggests that engaging in exercises, games, and other physical activities not only strengthens the body but also enhances the ability to apply knowledge practically in daily life, thereby fostering joy and personal development.

2. Moral Development: According to Vivekananda, education must prioritize the cultivation of moral virtues. It should nurture the innate qualities of love, compassion, and empathy within students. Moral development is crucial in sensitizing learners towards ethical conduct and fostering a sense of social responsibility. Vivekananda underscores the importance of instilling values such as altruism, courage, fearlessness, and integrity, as they contribute to the formation of a virtuous character. He sees ethics and religion as interconnected, with goodness being aligned with divine principles.

3. Intellectual and Mental Development: Swami Vivekananda emphasized the importance of intellectual and mental growth in education. He advocated for an educational system that equips students with the skills to be economically self-sufficient. Vivekananda believed in nurturing problem-solving abilities in learners, enabling them to navigate life's challenges successfully.

4. Emotional Development: Vivekananda highlighted the significance of emotional well-being in education. He recognized that emotional development strengthens individuals, enabling them to cope effectively with life's complexities. Education, therefore, should prioritize the emotional growth of students. It is essential for learners to understand and manage their emotions in various social situations. Thus, education should facilitate emotional intelligence and rational decision-making.

5. Spiritual Development: According to Vivekananda, education should also cultivate spiritual growth in students. It should foster moral values such as compassion, empathy, universal brotherhood, and tolerance towards diverse cultural backgrounds. Education, in Vivekananda's vision, instils the spirit of self-sacrifice and encourages individuals to transcend selfish desires for the betterment of society.

Aims of Education According to Vivekananda:

1. Cultivation of Moral, Spiritual, and Exemplary Character: Vivekananda passionately advocates for education's pivotal role in fostering moral integrity, spiritual depth, and the cultivation of exemplary character. Central to his vision is the conviction that education must not only enrich the intellect but also fortify the individual's moral fibre. Character formation, as per Vivekananda, is the cornerstone of personal evolution, nurturing virtues that transcend mere academic knowledge. He exhorts educators to instil lofty ideals, eradicate the seeds of negativity, and inspire students towards self-transcendence. In this pursuit, diligence, purity, an insatiable thirst for knowledge, unwavering faith, and an innate sense of humanity serves as indispensable guiding principles. Vivekananda underscores the profound responsibility of teachers in sculpting character while urging students to ardently seek wisdom from every corner of existence.

2. Empowerment for Self-Realization and Unfolding Potential: Vivekananda's vision of education radiates with the fervent belief in the inherent reservoir of knowledge within each individual. He champions the notion that education's true purpose lies in awakening the latent wisdom nestled within the recesses of the human psyche. Emphasizing self-reliance and self-development, Vivekananda invites learners on a transformative journey of self-discovery. Education, in his luminous perspective, serves as the catalyst for unveiling the boundless potential inherent in every soul. It empowers students to embark on a quest to unlock their inner treasures, thereby nurturing holistic growth and fulfilment.

3. Education for Physical Development: Vivekananda espouses the philosophy that a robust mind resides within a healthy body. He underscores the paramount importance of physical development as a key objective of education. According to him, holistic growth necessitates the harmonious development of both body and mind. Vivekananda extols Yoga as a precise science that enhances concentration and fosters emotional control, thereby nurturing overall well-being.

4. Education for Universal Brotherhood: Vivekananda passionately advocates for education to cultivate a sense of universal brotherhood among all individuals. He contends that neither an individual nor a nation can thrive in isolation from the wider community. Vivekananda emphasizes the imperative of nurturing a spirit of belongingness

among students, fostering harmony and fostering positive relationships with all nations. He inspires youth to combat societal inequalities and drive transformative social change.

5. The Practical Side of Life: Vivekananda stresses that education must not neglect the practical facets of life. He asserts that merely grasping lofty principles is insufficient; they must be applied in practical endeavours. Vivekananda champions the significance of agriculture, vocational arts, and practical skills in education, emphasizing the importance of translating theoretical knowledge into tangible action.

6. Education for Religious Development: According to Vivekananda, religious development constitutes a fundamental aim of education. He advocates for individuals to seek their absolute reality or truth, viewing religion as synonymous with self-realization. Vivekananda promotes a religion that harmonizes with scientific principles and instils patriotism. He advocates presenting the lofty ideals of saints to students, fostering a deep understanding of spirituality aligned with rationality.

6. Vocational Aim: Vivekananda underscores the necessity for individuals to attain self-sufficiency in earning their livelihoods. He prioritizes the vocational aim of education, envisioning a prosperous nation where every individual is self-reliant. Vivekananda emphasizes the importance of education in fostering economic independence, self-support, and self-sufficiency, empowering individuals to stand confidently on their own feet.

Relevancy of Swami Vivekananda's Educational Philosophy in the Present Scenario

Swami Vivekananda's profound insight into human nature, encapsulated in his belief that "Man is a compound of animality, humanity, and divinity," serves as a guiding beacon for modern education. He envisioned an educational system that nurtures individuals to transcend their animalistic instincts and embrace their divine potential through self-actualization, rational thinking, and comprehensive training. Today, Vivekananda's educational philosophies find resonance in various aspects of contemporary education:

1. Moral and Character Development: Vivekananda emphasized the pivotal role of character in shaping individuals into truth-seekers and responsible citizens. The modern education system echoes his sentiment by integrating value education into the curriculum, emphasizing moral and character development as essential components of holistic education.

2. Mental and Intellectual Development: Recognizing the significance of intellectual development in national progress, Vivekananda stressed the importance of fostering intellectual prowess among children. In today's rapidly advancing world, education focuses on intellectual growth, leveraging science and technology to equip learners with the knowledge and skills needed to thrive in a competitive global environment.

3. Physical Development: Vivekananda advocated for the holistic development of individuals, including physical well-being as a crucial aspect of self-realization. Contemporary education places significant emphasis on physical education, recognizing its role in promoting overall health and enabling individuals to engage in spiritual practices like Jnana Yoga, Bhakti Yoga, Karma Yoga, and Raja Yoga.

4. Mass Education: Vivekananda's vision for mass education, including women's education, vocational education, religious education, and national education, continues to inspire modern educational initiatives. Policies such as the Universalization of Elementary Education and the Right to Education Act, along with various vocational training programs, reflect his commitment to providing quality education to all segments of society.

5. Vocational Education: In line with Vivekananda's vision to eradicate poverty, vocational education has gained prominence in contemporary educational discourse. Various vocational training centers offer courses in fields such as teaching, engineering, fashion designing, tourism, and hotel management, empowering individuals to acquire skills for sustainable livelihoods.

6. Education for Universal Brotherhood and National Unity: Vivekananda's advocacy for universal brotherhood and national unity resonates deeply in today's multicultural society. Education plays a vital role in fostering respect for diversity and promoting harmony among individuals from different backgrounds. Through inclusive education initiatives and celebrations of cultural diversity, India progresses towards national unity and global peace.

Conclusion

In conclusion, education stands as the cornerstone of human development, serving as a transformative process that enhances knowledge, skills, and guides conduct, thoughts, and behaviours. Swami Vivekananda's visionary insight into the challenges facing the nation and his proactive initiatives towards nation-building exemplify his role as both a visionary and a creator. He not only identified the issues plaguing the country but also laid the groundwork for the emergence of a New India.

Vivekananda's profound understanding of Indian religion and philosophy in the context of modern times, coupled with his practical application of Vedanta principles to social service and reform, underscore his enduring legacy. His contributions to the Indian education system are commendable, with his educational philosophies resonating strongly in today's educational landscape. Vivekananda's emphasis on mass education and the empowerment of individuals to achieve self-reliance reflects the urgent need of the hour.

In essence, Swami Vivekananda's ideas continue to inspire and shape the present education scenario, serving as a beacon of enlightenment and progress. His vision of education as a means to empower individuals and enable them to stand independently is not only relevant but essential for steering the nation towards prosperity and societal well-being. Thus, Vivekananda's enduring legacy in the realm.

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